

Efficient SFW Oxy+ based e-fuel plant concepts

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Sumitomo SHI FW

Sumitomo SHI FW (SFW) introduction

SFW | A Finland Headquartered Energy Technology Company with Global Reach

1 800
employees
across the globe

20+
locations
around the world

130+
years of
experience

2017
Combining Finnish innovation with strategic Japanese corporate support

2014
Amec Acquires Foster Wheeler

1995
Foster Wheeler Acquires PyroPower

1978
A. Ahlström's first CFB

1891
Foster Wheeler founded

SFW response to decarbonization and climate change mitigation

Helping our customers to reach decarbonization goals

Energy Generation

Energy from biomass or waste for carbon neutral or carbon negative heat & power applications

Carbon Capture

Fleet of Carbon Capture technologies to decarbonize energy heavy industries

Gasification

Carbon neutral and waste feedstock into sustainable syngas, biofuels & chemicals, and plastics recycling

Energy Storage

Long Duration Storage – enabling net zero grid systems together with renewables

Services

Life cycle solutions enabling high plant availability and efficiency

Building a Net Zero Energy Ecosystem

The Sumitomo SHI FW Veturi (locomotive) development program

Booster by
**BUSINESS
FINLAND**

SFW Oxy+
development path to
demonstrated and
validated technology

Development path from small to large-scale designs since 2004

The CIUDEN SFW Oxy+ Carbon Capture Technological Development Plant (TDP)

A 30 MW_{th} Oxyfuel plant
in Ponferrada, Spain

A CCS demo plant with Endesa and
CIUDEN during 2009-2017

Design for a full-scale 300 MW_e plant
was developed as a part of the
project

Operational Experiences

List of globally located Oxy-CFB test facilities, as of 2017

SFW Oxy+ boiler island readiness

- CIUDEN Experience with oxy-fired operation from multiple pilot campaigns at 30 MW_{th} CFB testing facility both in 1st Gen and 2nd Gen operating modes verifying in large scale
 - Combustion process conditions in steady state (e.g. 1D, 3D models, emissions, SAFEC, combustion efficiency)
 - Dynamics; load change characteristics and switch over between the combustion modes
 - Operational experiences of SFW Oxy+ process and auxiliary equipment
- More recently widening the fuel spectrum by testing fuel specific characteristics of biomasses and waste fuels under oxy-fuel combustion at 1 MW_{th} scale CFB

Ongoing technology development within the NZEE: Expanding SFW Oxy+ for integrated CCUS facilities

Integrated SFW Oxy+ based e-fuel plant concept: Efficient and Flexible

SFW Oxy+ supporting e-fuel plant by utilizing waste O₂, providing biogenic CO₂ and electricity, (retrofitted) boiler remains fully capable to operate in air-fired mode as well if needed e.g. for supporting the power grid

Expansion of Oxyfuel combustion to Bubbling Fluidized Beds (BFB)

Fleet of BFBs typically with lower capacity than CFBs, i.e., better match in scale for the first e-fuel projects

BFB performance is improved in Oxyfuel combustion as the temperature profile becomes more even

SFW has, in collaboration with LUT University, conducted a 3D modeling study of Oxy-fuel combustion in BFBs utilizing in-house 3D model called "CFB3D" and Ansys Fluent.

The in-house model is validated against the data from Oxy-CFB experiments and demonstrations described above, and with the field measurements from SFW's air-fired BFB fleet.

The modeling results demonstrate that oxy-fuel combustion not only is viable for BFB applications but improves the performance as temperature profile gets more even and, consequently, hot-spots are avoided.

E-fuel plant scale-up and integration to Oxyfuel boiler, Oxy-boosting possibilities

For optimal integration of oxy-fuel combustion and e-fuel production, the capacities of electrolyzer and boiler plants should match, i.e., electrolyzer would supply all oxygen required for combustion, and synthesis plant would utilize all produced CO₂.

However, it always makes sense to utilize the side product O₂ instead of wasting it even if the quantity was not adequate for continuous operation under full oxyfuel combustion conditions.

Oxy-boosting will, depending on the extent, simplify the CO₂ purification concept and improve the energy efficiency of the carbon capture.

SFW and its partners are working on the concept optimization for different kind of oxy-boosting applications within the NZEE program.

Indicative ratio of fuel heat input MW_{fuel} (consuming the oxygen) compared to electrolyzer power MW_e (producing the oxygen)
Actual figure depends e.g. on performance of specific electrolyzer and on fuel spec

Thank you

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